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Transport Industry Psychosocial Risks and Controls

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KEYWORDS

Psychosocial work hazards
Transport workers
Mental health
Job stress
Risk control

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this research was to better understand the psychosocial hazards that could affect Australian transport workers, including road, rail, and shipping transport workers, and to develop a framework for psychosocial risk control measures for this population of workers. Data was collected from peer reviewed journal articles, web sites, and from industry partners that included Healthy Heads in Trucks and Sheds, Steering Minds, Tracksafe Foundation, Oz Help Foundation and the National Road Safety Partnership Program, as well as from Australian transport companies. Psychosocial hazards, health effects, and risk control measures were identified and a framework for psychosocial risk control measures developed. Recommendations are made to improve the management of psychosocial factors in the transport industries.

1. INTRODUCTION

Work-related psychosocial hazards are hazards that arise from, or relate to, the design and management of work, the work environment or plant, or workplace interactions and behaviour that may cause psychological harm (Western Australian Work Health and Safety (General) Regulations 2022 and Work Health and Safety (Mines) Regulations 2022, r 55A and 55B).

The McKell Institute in Queensland (Australia) from December 2022 to the end of February 2023, surveyed 1,036 transport workers either through a face-to-face interview or online interview. Results indicated that 76% of the respondents were concerned with their low pay with 45% struggling to afford to pay for food and their household living expenses as they were earning less than the minimum wage, and 74% of the respondents reported having to work long hours to make enough money to survive. Only 4% of the participants strongly agreed that they had job security. Of the 1,036 research participants 43% stated that they had been involved in a work-related accident and 55% reported experiencing threatening or abusive behaviour at work. Thirty six percent had experienced work-related injuries or work-related physical health issues, while 52% reported work-related stress, anxiety, or other work-related mental health issues (Reinhard, 2023). Pritchard et al. (2023) had similar findings and provided an explanation of financial stressors, particularly for casual workers and

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immigrant drivers (temporary visa holders) who were paid a minimum wage with no sick leave. For transport workers who have to hire their truck over the last 5 years there have been higher truck rental costs and overheads. There has also been lower profitability of loads resulting in some trucks being driven 24/7 with no roadside stop to be competitive to gain work. Truck drivers are only paid for items delivered and are not paid for waiting to unload their vehicle time, and waiting time could be more than 3 hours, which impacted their take home pay (Pritchard et al., 2023). Driving trucks is the most common work for Australian males, with one in 33 men being a driver (Van Vreden, et al, 2022).

Safe Work Australia (2023a) reported that between 2003 and 2021, 1076 road and rail drivers had been killed at work in Australia. This was the highest occupation for work related fatalities. Workers' compensation claims for serious injuries between 2008/09 and 2020/21 were 99,177 for road and rail drivers and during this period there were 1,802 workers' compensation claims for mental stress (Safe Work Australia, 2023b). The median time lost from mental health condition claims in 2020-21 (34.2 working weeks) was more than four times the median time lost across all claims (8.0 working weeks). The median compensation paid for mental health condition claims in 2020-21 (\$58,615) was close to four times the median compensation paid across all claims (\$15,743) (Safe Work Australia, 2023d). Workplace mental health conditions are one of the costliest forms of workplace injury as they lead to significantly more time off work and higher compensation paid when compared to physical injuries and diseases (Safe Work Australia, 2023d).

Changing workplace health and safety regulations, legislation and codes of practices have placed psychological health and safety as an important topic on workplace agendas. Traditionally the focus of workplace mental health approaches has been on intervening once an employee has developed a mental illness or supporting a return to work. The future approach to psychological health and safety will necessitate comprehensive organisational planning. Successful approaches require integrated frameworks to ensure promotion of mentally healthy work practice, prevention of psychosocial hazards, early intervention of developing mental health problems, and compassionate management of mental illness at work. Everyone has a role in managing psychosocial risks and in Western Australia these duties are set out in the Work Health and Safety Act (2020) and Regulations (2022).

This research was undertaken to better understand the psychosocial hazards that could affect transport workers, including road, rail and shipping transport workers, and to develop a framework for psychosocial risk control measures for this population of workers.

2. RESEARCH METHODS

2.1 Research aims

In 2023 research was commissioned by Toll Global Express with the aim of identifying:

- psychosocial hazards which may cause psychological or physical harm to transport workers,
- risks to the health or safety of transport workers from psychosocial hazards,
- risk control measures that are being implemented in industry to eliminate or minimise the risks.

2.2 Study population

The study population were Australian transport companies and road, rail, and shipping transport workers. Transport work is hard work with long, sedentary hours, shift work, fatigue and sleep deprivation which can take their toll on the health and wellbeing of professional drivers. Drivers in the transport industry commonly report problems such as insecure employment, loneliness, depression, chronic sleeping problems, excessive fatigue, and work stress from long hours and separation from family (Amoadu et al., 2023).

2.3 Data collection

To identify information to be able to achieve the research aims information was collected from peer reviewed journal articles, web sites including government web sites, and from industry partners that included Healthy Heads in Trucks and Sheds, Steering Minds, Tracksafe Foundation, Oz Help Foundation and the National Road Safety Partnership Program, as well as from transport companies. Industry organisations programs reviewed included Australia Post's Early matched care program, Work ready, Project me, Psychosocial working groups; Qube's Qube care, Zero harm policy, EAP Services; Linfox's Healthy Fox program, Core program, LEAP Program and DHL transport company's Mental health driver safety training, Fit for work, Fit for life and DHL4HER.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Industry review

The transport and logistics industry contributes 5% of GDP to the Australian Economy and employs over half a million people. In Australia 72% of the freight is carried by road (Chalmers, et al., 2021). Transport and logistics workers had the highest rate of compensation claim for work related mental disorders. Job insecurity is common in the transport industry, and this is stressful to professional drivers and impacts on sleep quality, insomnia and sleep disorders. This in turn causes drivers to work long hours with few recovery periods and may result in perilous behaviour on the road which include speeding and overloading, to meet employment contract expectations (Amoadu et al., 2023).

When interviewing drivers and their family members researchers at Monash University (2021) identified seven key areas that impacted on truck drivers physical and mental health. These were access to healthy food, exercise, and having enough sleep; stress of being on the road; quality of personal relationships; access to parking and rest facilities; conditions in their workplace; the regulations and policies that they had to follow, and the attitudes of people to truck drivers.

A meta-analysis conducted by Guest, et al. (2020) identified that ill-health risk factors for truck drivers included long working hours, long periods of time sitting with reduced opportunities for physical activity, irregular shift patterns, sleep deprivation, limited availability of healthy food, low levels of work control and intense work demands. Truck drivers were found to have chronic time pressures compounded by traffic conditions and delivery schedules to be met.

A study by Pritchard et al., (2020), was conducted by interviewing 17 truck drivers (who came from all Australian States and Territories), and 9 family members of the drivers. Results were analysed using NVivo software to identify the main answer themes of factors that impacted transport workers. Truck

drivers most important issue was the lack of availability of good fresh food when they were travelling and needed to stop for a meal. Drivers found it difficult when there were full parking bays, dangerous roads and they had to use dirty facilities. In terms of coping with the stress of their work drivers were reported by family members to go home with a lack of tolerance for other people ('short fuse'), not realising that this was due to their mental health. Drivers reported having difficulty in dealing with angry managers who did not respect them, and with members of the public who did not respect them and what they did for their work. Many of the drivers had relationship issues associated with being away from home due to work commitments. A work-related problem was that regulations (laws) meant that drivers were required to rest when alert and drive when sleepy. They wanted the ability to manage their own rest breaks (Pritchard et al., 2020),

Ill health in transport workers can be caused by vibration exposure which can damage muscles, joints and tendons, noise which can destroy the ability to hear, and by lifestyle factors such as working under the influence of alcohol or illegal drugs (HSE Global, 2023). For transport workers the most common ill health effects of their work were psychological distress (50%), chronic pain (44%), obesity (54.4%), poor general health (30%), overweight (25.2%), musculoskeletal disorders (44%), hypertension (25.8%) (Van Vreden et al., 2022; Useche, et al., 2019), sleep apnoea (26%) (Garbarino et al., 2018), hypersomnolence (excessive tiredness, Tucker et al., 2018), chronic fatigue (Ren et al., 2023), respiratory conditions including lung cancer, gastrointestinal disorders, metabolic syndrome, anxiety, depression (Useche, et al., 2019), cardiovascular diseases, (HSE Global, 2023) and reduced life expectancy (Guest et al., 2020). Research by Xia et al, (2021) found that 74.7% of transport drivers reported having a physical medical condition while 22.6% reported having a mental health condition. In 2022 there were 67 fatalities in the Australian transport industry, and this was the Australian industry that had the most work-related fatalities [34% of the work-related fatalities; 9.5 fatalities per 100,000 workers] (Safe Work Australia, 2023d)

A study by Xia, et al., (2021) identified that nearly half of the transport drivers had experienced at least one workplace violence incident in the past 12 months with verbal abuse being the most common violence. After construction workers, truck drivers were the most likely workers to commit suicide (OzHelp Foundation, 2020). Milner et al. (cited in Case, Alabakis, Bowles & Smith, 2020) examined coronial data relating to road and rail driver suicides in Australia between 2001 and 2010 and identified that there were 513 suicides among drivers within the study period.

3.2 Psychosocial hazards

According to regulation 55A of the Work health and safety general regulations in Western Australia (Department of Mines, Industry Regulation and Safety, 2022) a psychosocial hazard is a hazard that arises from, or relates to, the design or management of work or a work environment or plant at work or workplace interactions or behaviours and may cause psychological harm.

Workplace hazards that can cause psychosocial harm include organisational factors such as having poor organisational change management (Amoadu et al., 2023), inadequate reward and recognition for work performed [e.g., day pay rate, kms pay, job rate pay, contractual penalties if time slots are missed] (Workplace Health and Safety Queensland, 2020) and poor organisational justice. Safe Work Australia (2023c) provides examples of poor organisational justice as blaming workers for things that aren't their fault, or they can't control; not accommodating workers' reasonable needs; poor handling of workers information (e.g. not keeping personal information private); policies or procedures that are unfair, biased or applied inconsistently; failing to appropriately address (actual or alleged) issues (e.g.

inappropriate or harmful behaviour such as bullying), and decision-making processes that are poor or which workers aren't told about.

Job related psychosocial hazards can include lack of role clarity, role conflict (Tucker et al., 2018), work demands [such as time pressure and traffic delays] (Van Vreden et. al., 2022), emotional demands of the job (Dogbla et al., 2023), role overload (Tucker et al., 2018)], irregular work schedules, working long hours, job insecurity, and low job control (Amoadu et al., 2023). Workplace Health and Safety Queensland, (2020) describes problems with job control as occurring due to delays while waiting for the vehicle to be loaded or unloaded; lack of exclusion for truck drivers during unloading activities; time pressure; customer having unrealistic expectations about delivery times; sales deliverables incompatible with delivery requirements and legislation affecting the drivers breaks, which can be incompatible with schedules and can cause additional delays. Parikka (2023) reported that due to labour shortages and time pressures it was difficult for drivers to stop work to obtain the rest that they required to prevent fatigue.

Work behaviour psychosocial hazards can be the worker having poor support from supervisors and co-workers (Amoadu et al., 2023), having to deal with bullying, harassment, violence, aggression, conflict, or poor interpersonal relationships at work (Dogbla et al., 2023). Workplace Health and Safety Queensland, (2020) describes some of the common causes of aggression to transport workers as being poor communication and cooperation between parties and unsafe interactions with members of the public. Work environment psychosocial hazards can include having a poor physical environment (such as driving in bad weather conditions or dealing with other drivers' unsafe actions), experiencing traumatic events [such as motor vehicle accidents with cries for help from severely injured individuals and seeing mutilated bodies] (van Vreden et. al., 2022) or having remote work or isolated work (HSE Global, 2023). Having remote or isolated work can result in truck drivers having limited opportunities to exercise, poor sleeping arrangements, and limited access to nutritious food (van Vreden et. al., 2022). Transport drivers can spend long hours working on their own.

For the transport industry Workplace Health and Safety Queensland (nd.) reported 6 main types of psychosocial hazards. The first was low job control due to transport workers having limited choice of shifts, hours worked, ability to take scheduled breaks and limited choices over work deadlines, such as delivery times, particularly when there were unavoidable traffic delays. The second was high and low job demands due to demanding time pressures for pick up and deliveries, driving for extended periods of time without adequate rest causing fatigue, potential for monotonous dull work and exposure to traumatic events such as on road accidents and fatalities. The third type of hazard was having poor support due to being geographically dispersed and having reduced access to supervisor and coworkers' support, loading and unloading site design, poor site traffic management, lack of mechanical aids, poorly designed access and egress, load restraint problems such as inadequate or inconsistencies with customer loading and unloading restraint methods and time scheduling associated with customer demands and unforeseen delays. The next psychosocial hazard reported was low job clarity that may be caused by role conflict when attempting to meet client contract expectations and having inconsistencies in the work health and safety systems and requirements between their employer and clients. The fifth was poor organisational justice that could be perceived because of unfairness in the allocation of work shifts, differing work standards and requirements across the supply chain. The last type of psychosocial hazard described was poor relationships due to interpersonal conflicts (Workplace Health and Safety Queensland, nd.).

Internal to the organisation factors that can contribute to causing psychosocial harm include leadership. This is affected by the leaders (1) style and direction, (2) expectations and accountability, (3) psychological and social support, (4) involvement and influence in the organisation and (5) civility and respect shown. Another factor internal to the organisation is the organisational culture that is driven by the company mission, values and beliefs, the amount of openness and trust shown, management systems and processes and the care shown for employee health and wellbeing. The final factor internal to the organisation that can contribute to psychosocial harm is the behaviour of individuals. Behaviour includes individual competencies and abilities, individuals' growth and development goals, engagement, work-life balance and commitment to individual health and wellbeing goals and lifestyle (HSE Global, 2023).

Factors in the community environment can also cause psychosocial harm and include the economy (economic performance, Dogbla et al., 2023), labour market, inflation, competition and supply, the political environment (e.g., public opinion and performance) and social factors, such as housing supply and affordability, health system, lifestyle choices, recreational pursuits and behaviours (HSE Global, 2023).

In workplaces ways to identify psychosocial hazards occurrence include talking to workers, reviewing sick leave and annual leave to identify if there are any trends that indicate possible stress related causes. Interviews and a workplace survey can be conducted to identify psychosocial hazards.

Other ways to identify psychosocial hazards causing ill health effects include assessing if any areas of the business have higher levels of sick leave, if employees are using annual leave or long service leave for mental health conditions, if there are any workers' compensation claims for psychological injuries, and for the workplace employee assistance program if there are any trends or usage associated with mental health or stress related conditions.

It can be checked if there are in industrial related records any disputes associated with job stress or dissatisfaction, if there are complaints or grievances that are of a stress or mental health related manner and if issues have been raised formally in meetings or informally in relation to workload or changes to work roles.

It can be determined if there are any issues associated with excessive overtime or with fatigue, stress or working hours, if there are any departments reporting issues of under staffing, fatigue, or employee burnout, and if any department managers are reporting having too much work, conflicting time and work demands, or inappropriate behaviour.

It can also be assessed if workers are displaying signs of concern, being on edge or if any departments are having conflict or tension. Other way to identify psychosocial hazards in transport workplaces are included in the Safe Work Australia (2022) Code of Practice on Managing psychosocial hazards at work.

3.3 Survey results

A summary of the main psychosocial hazards in the Australian transport industry identified in the review of the following published literature are included in table 1.

This review identified that the most common psychosocial hazard identified from primary and secondary sources was job demands (89%, 8/9), followed by low job control (78%, 7/9) and the health-related impact of the work (68%, 6/9).

Table 1. Psychosocial hazards identified from primary and secondary sources.

Psychosocial Hazard	Resource (Primary and Secondary)								
	The Physical and mental health of Australian Truck Drivers (J.A)	Psychosocial work factors, road traffic accidents and risky driving behaviours in low and middle income countries. A scoping review	Occupational Risk Factors by Sectors: An Observational Study	Role stressors in Australian Transport and logistics workers: psychosocial implications	Sleep and Mental Health in Truck Drivers: Descriptive review of the Current and Proposal of Strategies for Primary Prevention	Industry specific Psychosocial Hazards and Factors - Transport industry	Physical and Mental Impacts on safety in the transport supply chain	5 Health and Safety Issues in the Transportation Industry	Mental illness in the transport industry- NRS
My Organisation									
Poor Organisational Justice	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Poor Change Management	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Inadequate Reward and Recognition	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
My Role									
Low Job Control	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Job Demands	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Lack of Role Clarity	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
My Team									
Poor Support	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Conflict, Poor Relationships	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Bullying and Harassment	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
My Environment									
Poor Physical Environment	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Traumatic events or material	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Remote or Isolated Work	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Violence and Aggression	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other									
External Factors Health related impact of the work	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

In table 2 are the results of published research where data was collected through interviews with transport workers.

Through interviews conducted as part of research studies it was identified by one third of the studies that the most reported psychosocial hazards for transport workers were inadequate rewards and recognition, job demands, poor team support, experiencing traumatic events, having remote / isolated work, and the health-related impacts of the work.

Information was sourced from professional transport organisations that included Healthy Heads in Trucks and Sheds, Steering Healthy Minds, Oz Help Foundation, Track Safe Foundation, and the National Road Partnership Program. Information from these organisations and four companies on psychosocial hazards that affected transport workers are included in table 3.

Table 3 shows that all (100%) of the professional organisations and companies reviewed described the work provided to the transport workers as having an impact on their health. The next most described psychosocial hazard was having poor team support (78%, 7/9) followed by having high job demands (56%, 5/9)

3.4 Psychosocial risk control measures being implemented in industry

Company One

A review conducted for psychosocial hazards at company one identified that the organisation had inadequate rewards and recognition for staff and poor change management. Staff reported having lack of role clarity, low work control and high job demands. In the work teams there was poor support, bullying and harassment. When an assessment of the work environment was conducted it was found that there was violence and aggression.

To meet risk control legal requirements company one developed programs to promote psychosocial health. Their first program was to form Psychological Safety working groups. Employees who were members of these working groups conducted psychosocial risk assessments and implemented risk control measures for any hazards identified. Program 2 was called Leadership@Post. This program is a multi-year commitment to strengthening leadership. Program 3 was to ensure that employees were work ready. This involved ensuring that any employee injured at work received prompt medical treatment and was provided with suitable work restrictions if this was required. Program 4 was early matched care that was designed to reduce secondary psychological injuries. Program 5 was called ProtectMe. This program is a career and personal development program for female staff members to give them the tools to build resilience, self-awareness, and career agility.

Company one now has a Stretch Reconciliation Action Plan to deliver indigenous (Aboriginal) employee parity. This plan is in action and includes inclusive recruitment, supporting indigenous education pathways, partnerships, and indigenous emerging leaders. Company one promotes and supports using indigenous traditional place names. Company one has a Rainbow Peer Support Group to support Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender, Queer, Intersex, and Asexual (LGBTQIA+) workers. The company one Inclusion Plan involves delivering on the company commitment to create an inclusive organisation for people with disabilities. The company one educational programs are designed to raise awareness, combat stigma, and build leadership capability to support psychological wellbeing. These programs have been reviewed and are now being expanded.

Company Two

The review at company 2 identified two hazards, one was poor organisational justice and the other was poor team support. To improve psychosocial health for employees this company has developed and implemented 4 programs. The first was called Healthy Company 2 Program. The 1st program was developed to connect team members with the tools and resources to help them make healthy mental and physical lifestyle choices. The program addressed 4 key topics. (1) Mental health. Mentally healthy minds in uncertain times webinars, mind fit workshops, Mental Health First Aid course, Employee Assistance Program and having a Mental Health Awareness Month. (2) General Health. This included having a vaccination program, bowel cancer prevention program, cancer awareness program, quit smoking programs, sun safety awareness and skin checks, men's health campaign and discounted private health insurance. (3) Nutrition. Educational workshops on nutrition, nutrition tip sheets, and the Avner's Foundation Remember September program. (4) Fitness and strength. Injury prevention fitness passport, correct move motivate challenge, and movement programs.

The 2nd program was a core company program and contained a series of safety topics that were designed to promote the company desired safety culture. These presentations have been given to all company teams over a 12-month period using existing meeting structures or toolbox talks at the workplace. The 3rd program, a site-specific program, was designed to provide intensive support to selected facilities. The site-specific program included an assessment of current processes and procedures, team surveys about safety culture, a 2 day 'illuminate' training program to upskill site leaders in safety tools that they could use to promote a positive safety culture and to develop site

specific safety culture plans. An employee assistance program for employees and their families to improve their mental and physical health and wellbeing was the 4th program.

Company Three

Hazards identified by the review at company 3 were poor organisational justice, poor team support and employee excessive behaviours that included the excessive use of alcohol, illegal drugs, and excessive gambling. Company 3's risk control programs were (1) Fit for work. Fit for life. This program encouraged employees to take care of their health and wellbeing. (2) Mental health driver safety training, which helped employees to learn resilience techniques and safe driving techniques. (3) The 4Her program was developed to encourage more women to consider a career in logistics and placed a heavy focus on nurturing the existing company female talent.

Company Four

Hazards identified by the Company 4 review were poor organisational justice, poor team support and bullying and harassment by team members. To deal with these hazards company 4 partnered with an employee assistance service provider to deliver evidence based practical solutions to increase accountability for personal wellbeing of the workforce, to improve employee health, happiness, and life satisfaction. A platform called Company Care was developed to create healthy workplaces and a culture of wellness. The company required everyone employed by the company to take responsibility, accountability, and care in interactions while at work. This platform included health promotion, increased awareness promotion of positive wellbeing, preventing and minimising the occurrence of work-related illnesses or injury and providing early intervention and support if these did occur. It included monitoring and prevention developing mechanisms and processes developed in consultation with workplace teams to monitor and prevent illnesses and injuries. The platform was also used to analyse job design to reduce risks and enhance protective factors. This company had a Zero Harm Policy to manage risks. In this policy the key focus areas were people, community, customers, the environment, plant and equipment.

Healthy Heads in Trucks and Sheds

Members of the professional transport organisation, Healthy Heads in Trucks and Sheds, identified the main psychosocial hazards as being transport drivers having lack of role clarity, high job demands, doing remote or isolated work, personal and home factors as well as addiction to alcohol, illegal drugs and excessive gambling.

The Mission of Healthy Heads in Trucks and Sheds is to create psychologically safe, healthy, and thriving working environments for truck drivers, distribution centre and warehouse staff, and other road transport workers. To achieve this mission and to promote risk control measures for the identified psychosocial hazards this organisation has developed and implemented a National Mental Health and Wellbeing Road map; guidelines for mental health and wellbeing strategies; handbooks for people leaders and the workforce and has a nutrition program called sharing the load and physical wellbeing.

To improve transport workers psychosocial health this organisation promotes driving awareness and reducing stigma; building mental health literacy through education; developing industry specific resources and by being an advocate for evidencing and profiling transport industry workers mental health needs and recommending solutions. Healthy Heads in Trucks and Sheds is working proactively to prevent or reduce the impact of mental health and wellbeing risk factors and, as a protection measure, to enhance workers strengths and capabilities and encourage early help seeking behaviour. It is promoting transport organisations to positively supporting and managing all mental health and wellbeing concerns, regardless of their cause.

Steering Healthy Minds

Psychosocial hazards identified by members of the organisation called Steering Healthy Minds, were having poor organisational support, lack of role clarity, high job demands but low job control, witnessing traumatic events, experiencing violence and aggression and doing remote or isolated work.

The mission of Steering Healthy Minds is to have a transport sector in which people are safe and healthy in their work. To achieve this mission and promote risk control measures for the identified hazards Steering Healthy Minds provides Mental Health First Aid (MHFA) and MHFA Engaging Leaders courses, and mental health peer to peer support. The transport sector Mental Health 1st Aid course was evaluated by researchers from the Central Queensland University (2022). The evaluation found that management were keen to support this program and considered it effective. Other workers reported that there needed to be better dissemination of information about the program throughout industry, that there was difficulty in workers obtaining the 12 hours required to attend the course and that in some organisations there was a lack of trust in management. Steering Healthy Minds is promoting ground support for transport workers who may be experiencing mental health concerns, normalising discussion on mental health issues in the transport industry so that it can be discussed in the same way as physical injuries and is supporting transport organisations to establish peer to peer mental health programs for workers.

Charmers et al. (2021) conducted research in which a questionnaire was completed by 60 heavy vehicle truck drivers who lived in Sydney, Australia. Statistical analysis of the answers was undertaken through a correlation analysis using SPSS. Analysis of answers identified a positive association between depression and alcohol use ($p = 0.044$), number of accidents while driving ($p = <0.004$) and number of hours driving per shift ($p = <0.001$). Anxiety was positively associated with the number of hours spent driving a week ($p = <0.001$) and the number of accidents experienced while driving ($p = 0.039$). Prolonged working hours are associated with raised salivary cortisol and raised cortisol levels are associated with depression. Drivers with depressive symptoms have difficulty in attention completing driving tasks as they have reduced arousal and activation of the somatic nervous system (Charmers et al., 2021). Current Western Australian Government Guidelines (2020) for commercial heavy vehicle drivers (regulation 3.132) allow heavy vehicle drivers to work 168 hours in a 14-day period that can include 17-hour work shifts. Research by Dinh et al., (2017) found that working more than 39 hours a week produced a decline in mental health. The research by Charmers et al. (2021) found that social interaction was negatively correlated with anxiety. Heinrichs et al., (2003) identified that as social interaction increases there is a biological suppression of the hypothalamic–pituitary– adrenal axis which results in a dampened cortisol effect, and this decreases stress. Long term positive social support was found by (Heinrichs et al., 2003) to have a significant anxiolytic effect, resulting in increased oxytocin release, and reduced cortisol release. This is a reason for the link between greater social support and reduction in anxiety as production of oxytocin is an underlying biological mechanism for the stress-protective effects of positive social interactions. Risk control measures suggested to decrease truck drivers' depression and anxiety included changing the rostering system to allow truck drivers to work better hours, providing toolbox talks and education about the effects of excessive alcohol consumption, and improving social support for truck drivers such as having a buddy system (Charmers et al., 2021).

Transport workers are employed in all Australian States and Territories. As a risk control measure, governments in Australia have included as a workplace legal responsibility, identifying, assessing, and controlling work related psychosocial hazards. Australian governments have developed Codes of Practice for managing psychosocial work-related hazards. Codes of Practice are not a legal requirement but provide guidance for employers and employees and are the minimum requirements expected to be

met by a court of law. Table 4 includes information about the relevant legislation and codes of practice in Australia used to manage psychosocial hazards in workplaces.

Table 4. Psychosocial Health Legislation and Codes of Practice in Australia

	WA	QLD	NSW	VIC	SA	NT	TAS	ACT
Code of Practice (COP) Status	Active Dec-22	Active April-23	Active Oct-22	Proposed TBC	No COP	Active July 2023	Active Dec-22	No COP
Associated Regulations Status	Dec-22	WHS 2011	Oct 22	April 2023	No State Regulation	Jan 2023	Dec-22	July 2022
Legislation	March-22	Oct-22	Oct-22	2004 OHS Act	2012 WHS Act	2011 WHS Act	2012 WHS Act	2011 WHS Act
Legislation/ COP Specifics	COP: Psychosocial hazards in the workplace COP: Violence and aggression in the workplace COP: Workplace Behaviour COP: Mentally Healthy workplaces for FIFO workers	COP: Managing the risk of psychosocial hazards at work WHS Regulation Section 55A COP: Preventing and managing fatigue in the workplace Guide: Preventing and responding to workplace bullying.	COP: Managing psychosocial hazards at work COP: How to manage work health and safety risks WHS ACT: Section 274	Guide: Preventing and managing work-related stress: A guide for employers Document: Understanding mental health in the workplace. Fact Sheets: Fatigue, Bullying, Work-related Violence, Stress	Checklist: Psychological health safety checklist Checklist: Wellbeing Safety Scan Mental Health Act 2009 Guide: Preventing and responding to work-related violence guide Resource: People at Work	COP: How to manage work health and safety Risks	Resource: People at Work Resource: Head4Work Campaign: 2019 Safety is Everything campaign	Strategy: Managing Work- Related Psychosocial Hazards 21-23. Plan: Managing Work-Related Violence and Aggression Plan 21-23 Plan: Managing Work-Related Sexual Harassment Plan 21-23 Policy: Compliance and Enforcement Policy 20-24
Reference to Safe Work Australia (SWA) and other organisations	References risk management process adapted from SWA	SWA Guidance: The health and safety duty of an officer. SWA Guide: How to determine what is reasonably practicable to meet a health and safety duty. SWA Guide preventing and responding to workplace bullying.	SWA Principles of Good Work Design SWA Work-related psychological health and safety: A systemic approach to meeting your duties		SWA: Psychological health and safety and bullying in Australian workplaces. SWA: Preventing psychological injury under work health and safety laws. WorkCover QLD	SWA: Work related psychological health and safety: A systemic approach to meeting your duties. SWA Guide: Preventing and responding to workplace bullying.	SWA: Psychosocial health and safety and bullying in the workplace Report. WorkCover QLD RU, OK?	SWA: how to manage work health and safety risks code of practice. SWA: work-related psychological health, a systematic guide to meeting your duties. SWA: preventing psychological injury under WHS Laws

Table 4 shows that it is a legal requirement to manage psychosocial hazards in the workplace in Western Australia, Queensland, New South Wales, Northern Territory, Tasmania and in the Australian Capital Territory. Managing psychosocial hazards is not specifically included in the Victorian or South Australian law. Western Australia has four Codes of Practice related to managing psychosocial hazards while Queensland, New South Wales, and the Northern Territory each have one.

In the framework below for psychosocial risk control measures for the transport industry the most common hazards identified were job demands (red box, high risk), followed by conflict, poor relationships, and poor support (orange box, medium risk). The remaining risks documented in table 5 (yellow boxes) were deemed as lower risk psychosocial hazards in the Australian Transport industry as they occurred less often. All psychosocial hazards have appropriate risk control measures to be implemented included in this framework. Based on risk control measures identified from primary, secondary, industry and professional organisations the following table of risk control measures for psychosocial hazards has been developed.

Table 5.

Psychosocial Hazard Controls Identified	
<p style="text-align: center;">Job Demands</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policies and Procedures • Clear and Specific Expectations to be set in consultation with the workforce • Reduce unrealistic demands • Individual action Plan • Consultation with workers and clients on schedules and delivery expectations • Monitoring of fatigue and sleep resultant from work schedules and rostering • Implement fitness for work for employees who have repeated fatigue incidents/alerts • Monitor workloads and provide additional support over peak periods 	<p style="text-align: center;">Poor Support</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Appropriate Support Systems – including peer support systems in addition to EAP programs, such as establish social connections • Leadership and Development • Promote early intervention • Improved loading and unloading across all sites • Review of site design and traffic management to improve delivery/operations, including access and egress to trucks etc. • Ensure access to mechanical aids to improve delivery/operations • Consistency across all sites and clients in terms of load restraint management • Ensure workers have the tools and resources to perform the role
<p style="text-align: center;">Conflict / Poor Relationships</p> <p>Communication and consultation to reduce future conflict and tension</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mitigate Workplace stressors and risks • Invest in corporate leadership programs • Clear and consistent leadership systems to support employees – build leadership capability • Review and development in corporate culture growth and development • Development of Civility and Respect • Diversity and inclusion awareness and integration across the business • Set clear rules and behaviour to reduce conflict • Implement initiatives to improve mental health within the organisation • Identify sources of conflict with the view to assess and implement appropriate controls • Improved change management to reduce conflict and ambiguity • Improve communication of commitment to improving health and wellbeing within the organisation 	<p style="text-align: center;">Low Job Control</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve controls worker has over job • Flexible work schedules, job flexibility and decision making • Consultation with the workforce and clients to reduce delays associated with loading and unloading and associated time pressures • Clearly identify client expectations to ensure realistic and appropriate • Remove discrepancies between sales deliverables and delivery abilities • Legislated driver breaks.
<p style="text-align: center;">Inadequate Reward and Recognition</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Team focused activities • Career progression • Incentive Programs • Reward integrity and effort • Recognise and thank employees for their work • Ensure payment arrangements reflect working environments – (e.g. significant delays • Review of remuneration and employment of drivers – (e.g. day rates, kms and job rate) 	<p style="text-align: center;">Violence and Aggression</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policies and Procedures • Appropriate Support Systems • Identify sources of violence and with the view to assess and implement appropriate controls • Work with industry partners to implement education and preventative programs • Reduce problems associated with deliveries that create tension - delays, lack of equipment, traffic management,
<p style="text-align: center;">Lack Of Role Clarity</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clear Job Descriptions • Performance Reviews • Clear and consistent leadership and management of work and team 	<p style="text-align: center;">Poor Organisational Justice</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthening work across diverse communities • Commitment from senior organisational leaders • Policies and procedures • Improve working conditions that cause health problems – working conditions • Look to reduce irregular work schedules to workers • Decrease financial pressures to be on time at the lowest cost.
	<p style="text-align: center;">Employer Health Initiatives</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support of an Occupational Physician to implement health prevention, monitoring and education programs to reduce the impact on health for both work-related and non-work-related factors • Engage with industry partners to invest in Leadership programs improve road condition, safety and education programs to target critical safety and health risks. • Health Surveillance programs • Commitment from Senior organisational leaders regarding improving health and wellbeing initiatives within the business – including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Health and wellbeing ✓ Suicide prevention ✓ Mental health
	<p style="text-align: center;">Poor Change Management</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication and Consultation • Implementation of clear and appropriate change management process
	<p style="text-align: center;">Remote or Isolated Work</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establish internal supports and social connections • Access to peer support programs in addition to EAP • Consultation with remote and isolated workers to implement systems to support employees
	<p style="text-align: center;">Bullying and Harassment</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policies and Procedures • Promoting a safe/positive workplace culture • Set clear rules on communication and cooperation with all stakeholders • Identify sources of Bullying and harassment with the view to assess and implement appropriate controls
	<p style="text-align: center;">Traumatic Events of Material</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policies and Procedures • Appropriate Support Systems • Psychological Debriefing • EAP Services
	<p style="text-align: center;">Poor Physical Environment</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policies and Procedures • Appropriate Support Systems to workers who work remotely or independently; • Improved good sleeping arrangements. • Work with work with remote restaurants to improve menu and nutrition offered.

As a risk control measure for transport workers experiencing traumatic events Bouzikos, et al., (2022) recommended having peer support from other transport workers who had previous similar experiences as it appeared that employee assistance programs had a lack of information to effectively implement primary prevention strategies for psychological distress, depression, anxiety and for post-traumatic stress disorder. Research conducted by Bryant (2023) agreed with this as it was found that well-meaning employee assistance programs may not help and could result in harm if people are provided with early debriefing when their stress hormones are highly active as debriefing can consolidate their trauma memories. Bryant (2023) reported that providing psychological first aid through peer support was a better option as this does not encourage people to disclose their emotional response to the trauma but provides them with someone to talk to and support as required.

Pritchard et al., (2023) conducted 17 interviews with Australian truck drivers to identify personal the coping strategies that drivers used to deal with mental health issues. The first coping strategy identified was to have connections with family, work colleagues, friends and with trained professionals as required. Other personal coping strategies used included appreciating the moment, being grateful for what they had, being optimistic, having a high level of internal locus of control, having mental toughness, and having resilience.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

4.1 Conclusions

The first research aim was to identify psychosocial hazards which may cause psychological or physical harm to transport workers. Conclusions related to this aim are that the main psychosocial hazards for

transport workers were high job demands, dealing with conflict, poor relationships, poor support, low job control, poor organisational justice, lack of role clarity, poor workplace change management, and having a poor physical environment. Other important psychosocial hazards identified were transport workers having to deal with violence and aggression, bullying and harassment, witnessing or being part of traumatic events, having remote or isolated work, and having inadequate rewards and recognition for their work.

The next research aim was to identify risks to the health or safety of transport workers from psychosocial hazards. Conclusions were that psychosocial hazards could cause psychological distress, poor general health, hypertension, hypersomnolence, chronic fatigue, anxiety, depression, suicide, and other mental and/or physical health conditions. In relation to safety, it was concluded that if transport workers were not well then, they were more likely to be less alert and have accidents that may injure or kill themselves or other people.

The final research aim was to identify risk control measures that are being implemented in industry to eliminate or minimise the risks. The risk control measures used in industry are documented in 3.4 in this paper. It was concluded that risk control measures being implemented in industry can be grouped into 5 main categories. Category (1) were mental and physical health promotion programs. (2) Employee assistance programs, mental health first aid, and other programs that provided employees with support once they had mental health problems. (3) Programs that promoted a culture of care and a positive workplace safety culture. (4) Programs that helped employees to learn resilience techniques, self-awareness, career agility and (5) programs that included analysing job design to reduce risk and enhance protective factors. The 5th category of programs looked at eliminating the risk of psychosocial hazards and it was concluded that this was an effective risk control measure.

4.2 Recommendations

It is recommended that to optimise employee health and minimise psychosocial hazards in the workplace a person-centred approach should be used and psychosocial hazards in the workplace should be identified. The Safe Work Australia (2022) Code of Practice Managing psychosocial hazards at work is useful to do this. It is recommended that transport companies should aim to improve safety and not harm employees' physical or mental health, improve social and emotional wellbeing of their employees, prevent work related causes of mental and other work related illnesses, focus on early detection and appropriate intervention if work related illnesses occur and improve employee access to high quality services and employee support if this is required to deal with employee psychosocial or other work related issues. The amount of work and the hours of work that transport workers perform should be realistic (not cause fatigue) and appropriately paid for, while still maintaining company profitability.

In the workplace it is recommended that managers and workers respect each other. It is essential that there is commitment from top management to eliminating psychosocial hazards in their workplace, promote and resource mentally healthy workplaces. Employees have firsthand experience of work-related psychosocial hazards so management should consult with, and listen to, employees when determining risk control measures. Other recommendations are for transport companies to determine what is currently in place to eliminate or minimise psychosocial hazards and look at what future initiatives are already planned. Transport companies should then decide what information they can use to assist them to identify psychosocial hazards for their company, to determine what risk control measures are best for their business, determine implementation strategies, educate employees for change, determine what resources and time frames are required to implement the risk control measures,

implement the risk control measures and determine how psychosocial risk identification and control processes interplay with employee health management strategies. Once risk control measures have been implemented, they need to be evaluated to ensure that they are effective and to determine any opportunities for improvements to be implemented. Future initiatives can then be planned. There needs to be ongoing communication of company commitment, plans and actions to employees, clients, and other stakeholders in relation to minimising the occurrence of psychosocial hazards.

Transport workers are also affected by government decisions. The government needs to listen to transport workers' concerns, particularly in relation to fatigue management regulations which are not effective. Governments are recommended to have safe, well-maintained roads and rail networks. In relation to having good fresh food it is recommended that drivers map on their route where good fresh food can be purchased and if this is not available, they would need to pack up their own food to eat. In the places that truck drivers need to park premises owners should provide available appropriate parking spaces for deliveries to be made safely.

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